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Green building materials: a new frontier in data-driven sustainable concrete design

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Abstract

This paper presents a novel approach for developing sustainable building materials through ecologically informed Sequential Learning. Large data sets with different types of alkali-activated building materials, including fly ash and blast furnace slag-based concrete, were compiled from the literature to develop and evaluate this approach. Based on these data an extensive experimental study was conducted to compare the performance of the proposed material design methods under simulated laboratory conditions derived from real-world scenarios. The results indicate a significant reduction in development time and lower research costs enabled through predictions with machine learning. This work challenges common practices in data-driven materials development for building materials. Our results show, training data required for data-driven design may be much less than commonly suggested. Further, it is more important to establish a practical design framework than to develop more accurate models. This approach can be immediately implemented into practical applications and can be translated into significant advances in sustainable building materials development.

HIGHLIGHTS

- Innovative approach to designing sustainable building materials using ecologically informed sequential learning.
- Provides clear guidance for design process, can advance sustainable material development immediately.
- Challenges data-driven materials dev. practices by prioritizing practical design frameworks over accurate models.
- Results: significant reduction in development time, lower research costs, and straightforward predictions through sequential learning.
- Large data sets of different types of alkali-activated building materials used for evaluation.
- Extensive experimental study conducted to compare performance of proposed material design methods.

1 Introduction

The use of computer modeling has revolutionized the field of civil engineering, allowing engineers to design their most complex and ambitious designs from the comfort and affordability of their desks. This has brought a new era of design capabilities. However, materials development has not kept pace with the digital revolution that has taken place in the construction industry since the 1960s. The inherent complexity and variability of building materials make them difficult to model and analyze, which has historically limited the development of new materials to labor-intensive laboratory testing. This is a major bottleneck in construction innovation, with far-reaching consequences due to the significant contribution to CO₂ emissions of materials in use today.

The highest emissions come from the production of Portland cement, which alone is responsible for around eight percent of anthropogenic emissions [1]. Unlike most materials, the emissions from cement production result from the burning process and the decarbonization of limestone. International environmental goals such as the European Green Deal [2] aim to reduce these emissions to achieve carbon neutrality in Europe by 2050.

Newly developed cementitious binders low in calcium can reduce carbon dioxide emissions by 40-80 percent while maintaining comparable structural properties to traditional cement [3]. However, developing these new binders, commonly known as alkali-activated materials (AAM) or geopolymers, is challenging. AAMs can be synthesized from a large variety of aluminosilicate feedstocks and a wide range of activator solution compositions to achieve the desired properties. This way, binders with varying properties suitable for various applications can be obtained. However, this large variety makes it difficult to develop these new formulations in a feasible timeframe. Each raw material and binder could require batch-wise adjustment in the laboratory, which is very time-consuming given the complex nature of the underlying chemical reactions.

Another critical concern is that the future availability of well-established substitutes is uncertain. In particular, the quantities of fly ash will diminish in the foreseeable future because many countries are approaching the end of coal-fired power generation [4, 5]. Additionally, due to the conversion of blast furnaces to hydrogen, the composition of granulated blast furnace slag substitutes will also differ significantly from the currently known [6]. This could lead to production losses and setbacks and even undo the progress made so far in the ecological transformation of Portland cement.

In the future, alternatives such as secondary raw materials, recycled materials and industrial by-products from various sources and processes could be used as binder components. The decision criteria for their application are not only given by material properties but also by material costs - monetary and environmental. These, in turn, depend on processing, source location, and material recovery. It has been shown that cost-critical components can be added and replaced with new ones in more complex mixed material systems, further increasing the overall economics of greener building materials [7]. Nevertheless, using many new raw materials and their combinations, both with each other and with additives and possibly other stimulants, leads to an exponentially growing number of possible compositions. The synthesis and experimental characterization of these compounds would exceed the capacity of current lab-based experimental exploration.

Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based materials design methods solve the problem of optimally tuning formulations much more efficiently. Rather than relying solely on a time-consuming laboratory validation, optimization frameworks such as Sequential Learning (SL) and the closely related Bayesian Experimental Design (BED) [8] create a data-driven feedback loop: From a variety of possible formulations, SL predicts the most promising candidate materials, which are then empirically validated in the laboratory. The predictive models have been trained again with the empirical results from the laboratory to make better suggestions in the next round. Instead of calculating the parameters for an ideal formulation directly, Machine Learning (ML) models optimize formulations in an iterative cycle of predictions and validations.

Although the complexity of the building materials tuning does not yet permit a purely computer-aided design, it reduces the number of samples with undesirable properties. Formulations that do not provide valuable information or have little chance of success are discarded from the outset, resulting in more efficient use of limited lab resources. Moreover, SL makes it possible to improve many material properties simultaneously and to include critical socioeconomic factors such as carbon footprint, material costs, or resource availability as optimization criteria. In this way an ideal concrete precisely tailored to its purpose can be developed quickly while considering the given market conditions.

1.1 Novelty, Scope, and Research Approach

This paper presents a large-scale investigation of the feasibility and practicality of developing alternative building materials with SL. The goal is to provide a guide on how SL optimization can be performed successfully against the constraint of a real-world laboratory.

Virtual experiments for SL-driven concrete design were conducted to measure the performance in terms of the number of iterations (or development cycles) needed to find a material with desired properties. These experiments were repeated with randomized starting conditions and were assessed statistically. The candidate materials chosen by SL at each development cycle were taken from previously reported laboratory results in the literature.

The data for these experiments were compiled from 49 sources, comprising 1,367 formulations for alkali-activated concrete. For each formulation, the resulting compressive strength from the laboratory is available - one of the critical properties of concrete. In addition, the data was enriched by including CO₂ footprints based on literature values.

Two common predictive SL models were compared, Random Forest regression (RF) and Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) and the effectiveness of different pre-processing and model-tuning pipelines was investigated. Further, two search strategies for SL were compared, one relying solely on model predictions, to sample the next composition, and the other deliberately exploring uncertain compositions by considering both the predictions and their uncertainties.

To investigate the ideal size of initial training data sets in SL-based materials design all experiments were performed with 4 and 20 initial samples, respectively. The design target was, on the one hand, naively based on strength predictions only and, on the other hand, informed by the carbon footprint of the material.

The results provide hope for a much-needed opportunity to accelerate the "time to solution" for new climate-friendly building materials.

2 Points of Departure

This chapter summarizes the literature and previous work and lays out the hypothesis, research questions and goals for exploration of this contribution.

2.1 Literature Review

Previous studies have demonstrated that achieving high-quality building materials with acceptable socio-economic impact is possible. For instance, by varying base materials and optimizing synthesis pathways it is possible to improve both the performance and the ecological footprint of alternative materials such as alkali-activated concretes (AAC) [7, 9, 10]. However, as Firdous et al. point out in [11], the number of possible alkali-activated concrete formulations based on commonly used supplementary cementitious materials is beyond human capacity to test in the lab.

In addition, small changes in curing conditions, mixing methods, and material supply have a significant impact on the properties of the materials. Unfortunately, reliably predicting these properties is not feasible in general due to the underlying complexity of the composition and the production process. At the same time, recent environmental goals such as the European Green Deal, encourage the use of alternative raw materials resources to achieve a green circular economy. Thus, alternative approaches to designing and manufacturing building materials are urgently sought after.

Because of the many different constituents contained in typical building materials and the subsequent variety in their properties, a computer-aided approach to material design was considered early [12]. However, predictions based on empirical data were not possible at that time. The recent advent of ML methods in concrete science and increases in computing power have expanded the possibilities for material design. Naderpour et al. [13] utilized Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) to predict the compressive strength of environmentally friendly concrete mixtures. Chaabene et al. [14] reviewed the effectiveness of different ML techniques, including ANNs, support vector machines, decision trees, and evolutionary algorithms, in predicting concrete properties. Li et al. [15] provide a survey of applications and best practices in the field as of 2022, emphasizing the significance of data preparation, model validation, and their interpretation.

In the field of concrete based 3D printing, Sergis et al. [16] employed a combination of ANNs, genetic algorithms, and Pareto optimization to find mixtures with optimal properties. Similarly, Golafshani et al. [17] combined genetic algorithms and decision tree ensembles to find concrete mixtures incorporating rubber that maintained compressive strength while reducing CO₂ emissions. Related techniques were used to predict novel concrete mixtures that aim to reduce costs [18] and CO₂ footprint [19].

Further, a recent article uses generative design and genetic algorithms to optimize the topology and steel reinforcement of concrete beams leading to promising results with respect to saving costs and improving the environmental footprint [20]. A detailed review on combining ML algorithms with evolutionary approaches is summarized by Song et al. [21].

Although these frameworks propose new promising compositions, they suffer from a major drawback, as they rely on training ML algorithms on sufficiently large data sets (~1000 datapoints). Collecting this data is costly and time-consuming, especially in the field of building materials as elaborative experiments need to be performed to obtain the data. Furthermore, the varying composition of the precursor materials add additional optimization challenges. These challenges are also analysed in detail by Li et al. [15].

SL has successfully adapted to complex new scenarios while getting by with relatively little training data [8, 22]. Ling et al. [23] demonstrated the potential of SL in materials discovery across multiple domains, excluding concrete. Later, Rohr et al. [24] benchmarked SL for applications in electrochemistry, comparing its performance to that of GPR, RF, and Linear Ensemble Regressors. They found that SL can significantly accelerate materials discovery when used properly, but caution against potentially negative effects if certain aspects of the model are not carefully chosen. In the context of building materials, Völker et al. [25] investigated the use of SL for detecting alkali-activated binders and found it to be highly effective, requiring up to 60 times fewer data and processing more than three times as many features as conventional ML methods. This suggests superior performance in complex real-world scenarios. Von Rueden et al. [26] pointed out that integrating prior knowledge in ML models can benefit various research areas. Völker et al. [27] demonstrated that incorporating known material parameters as a knowledge-based loss term is valuable in guiding the search for environmentally friendly building materials.

Despite these promising results, there is no comprehensive understanding of the potential performance capabilities of data-driven building material design with sequential learning. The scarcity of available samples, the complex, diverse nature of starting materials, and the high cost of experimentation pose challenges for extensive data-driven work. The incomplete characterizability of these materials adds to the uncertainties, which may have hindered the adoption of data-driven approaches in the laboratory to date.

Despite these challenges, there is a significant opportunity to explore and demonstrate the potential of sequential learning for building materials in various scenarios. This knowledge gap presents an opportunity for further research to better comprehend the potential of using SL in construction.

2.2 Hypothesis, Research Question, Goals for Exploration

The central hypothesis of this study is that the configuration of the AI-driven materials design (e.g., in terms of model selection, hyperparameter settings, and selected strategy) has a significant impact on the expected performance. To probe this hypothesis, we aim to answer the following research questions that will help us to better understand the potential and limitations of SL in this context:

1. What is the impact of:
 - a. Limited training data points commonly available for concrete testing on the effectiveness of SL?
 - b. Incorporating socio-economic information on the performance of SL in finding optimal AACs?
 - c. Using classical Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) models compared to Random Forest (RF) models for a given scenario, and can automated pipelines for model optimization and feature selection further enhance SL performance?
 - d. Exploratory, uncertainty-based techniques compared to point estimator predictions in finding optimal AACs, and under what circumstances is one approach more effective than the others?
2. How effectively can SL accelerate the search for optimal AAC?
3. Considering that only a small portion of the training data is labeled at the end of a material design run, how well do the different models generalize to the remaining data points?

The performance of SL algorithms is highly dependent on the underlying data set and optimization target [28]. In this study, we aim to evaluate the potential benefits of using SL for finding optimal AACs, and for identifying solution strategies that can maximize the performance of these algorithms in specific cases. This research will address the challenges of working with small training samples, high-dimensional input data, and

discontinuous batches of material, which violates many of the traditional assumptions and practices of ML in the independent and identically distributed (IID) regime. By providing insights into the effectiveness and potential applications of SL in this context, we hope to improve the understanding of the role of configuration and other factors in the performance of these algorithms. In addition to offering guidance for solving domain-related problems, this study may also inspire solution strategies for addressing complex ML problems with small data.

3 Research method

Traditional material development workflows typically start by developing the formulation (i.e., prescriptive-based material compositions) to achieve the desired properties - such as a minimum compressive strength - that can be validated in the laboratory. However, predicting the material composition can be challenging for various reasons [29]. First, formulations often need to be better-conditioned, i.e., small changes in composition can significantly affect the resulting material properties. Second, numerous non-unique solutions exist where completely different compositions with different amounts of constituents result in the same target properties. Finally, the number of constituents in the solution is not fixed, making a closed-form solution unattainable.

The Inverse Design (ID) approach is a viable method for addressing these challenges. It involves screening a set of given formulations and iteratively identifying optimal compositions based on how well their predicted properties align with the target requirements. This approach turns the material development process around by optimizing the predicted target property rather than the composition. As a result, ID has the potential to uncover novel materials that meet the desired specifications but would not be apparent through traditional design workflows.

This chapter describes the implementation of the ID approach using SL and highlights the differences in benchmarking SL and the underlying models. The data on which this work is based is also presented.

3.1 Description of the SL-guided materials design tasks

SL-based ID uses a prediction model to guide the selection and evaluation of material formulations to identify optimal material properties. This iteratively improves the properties of the material by following the steps in Figure 1.

1. Creating a materials search space or design space (DS) that contains the formulations of viable materials that can be considered for the desired outcome.
2. Training an ML model to predict the properties of materials based on their composition and structure using the initial training data. Viable models include GPR for BED, and RF or any other suitable regression algorithm for SL.
3. Selecting additional samples for characterization using ML prediction weights by acquisition function, also known as a sample utility function.
4. Experimentally validating the selected samples in the laboratory.
5. If the criteria are not met, updating the ML model with the new data, and repeating the process allowing for continuous improvement in the known material's properties.
6. If the criteria are met, the design task is finished.

Figure 1: Steps of the sequential learning inverse design loop

The DS should be extensive and inclusive yet limited to material formulations that are physically feasible to produce. The initial training data is obtained by selecting and characterizing a representative subset of the entire material space, serving as the starting point for the ML model.

The design process is guided towards target criteria at each iteration using a utility function. This function assigns weights to candidate materials based on their predicted properties and any available prior information. The closer the predicted result aligns with the desired value, the higher the weight assigned to the material. Additionally, the utility function may consider prediction uncertainty, which is crucial in discovering new

relationships and supporting experimentation decisions. As Reyes et al [30] aptly put it, if the outcome of an experiment is already certain, there is no reason to conduct it, and an experiment is more useful if the uncertainty of the outcome is significant. All three factors (prediction, uncertainty, and a-priori information) are included in the utility function in equation (1).

$$u_i = \mu_i + w * \sigma_i - A_i \quad (1)$$

where μ_i corresponds to the normalized predicted material property (e.g., compressive strength), $w * \sigma_i$ is the weighted uncertainties of the i -th prediction and A_i are the normalized a-priori information (e.g., carbon emissions). This formula applies to Multi-Objective Optimization (MOO) scenarios. It calculates the joint performance based on the normalized sum of targets, which includes predicted material properties and a priori information. Normalizing the targets to a common scale enables fair comparison of otherwise disparate quantities during the optimization process. Objectives that are to be minimized, such as carbon emissions, are given a negative sign to reflect the preference for materials with lower CO2 to have higher utility. In Single Objective Optimization (SOO), only the predicted material property is sought, resulting in A_i being omitted.

The prioritization of the next candidate x_{n+1} is done by choosing the maximum value according to equation (2).

$$x_{n+1} = \operatorname{argmax}(u) \quad (2)$$

This systematic exploration of the space of possible material compositions allows directly identifying materials with the desired properties. There are two predominant configuration strategies: exploratory and exploitative. The exploratory strategy is characterized by a high weight of uncertainty, which is intentionally leveraged to acquire new information rapidly. In contrast, the exploitative strategy is focused on utilizing the predictions of the SL model to attain the desired outcome with a higher probability of success, which necessitates robust predictive performance. Thus, the choice between the two strategies often involves balancing the trade-off between acquiring new information and exploiting the model's predictions. Further information on this approach can be found in [8] and [30].

3.2 Benchmarking SL

The effectiveness of SL can be demonstrated through simulated experiments where the true results for all data points are known. In these experiments, only a subset of the available data is provided to the SL algorithm. Additional data points are added in each development cycle based on the algorithm's decision of the most promising data point. The optimization's success is measured by the required number of development cycles to find materials with the desired target properties.

The number of SL cycles required depends on the initial conditions of the experiment, which results in a distribution of the required number of development cycles. This distribution can evaluate statistical performance, for example, by determining the average number of cycles required to achieve the optimization goal. In this study, the 90th percentile indicator was chosen for the results expected in the laboratory - this corresponds to a point in the distribution where 90% of the SL runs achieved the target. The relatively high 90th percentile benchmark means that there is a high probability that the target can be reached within the obtained number of SL cycles.

SL is typically compared against a random draw (RD) as a baseline benchmark. In RD, experiments are carried out without a strategy or model, and the probability of success can be estimated using the hypergeometric distribution. More details on benchmarking SL can be found in [25].

3.3 Benchmarking the Prediction Model

In addition, the predictive performance for the different model and pipeline combinations are evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R-squared) [31]. This metric measures the performance of the model by comparing the predicted and actual values of a dataset. The dataset is divided into two parts: a training set and a test set. The training set is used to build the model, while the test set is used to evaluate its performance on unseen data.

Two scenarios are compared: (1) a baseline performance obtained using a random 70/30 training/test-split of the data, and (2) the model's prediction on the remaining data points at the end of each SL run. In scenario (1), the training set is split into 25 randomly selected folds, a common practice that assumes Independence and Identically Distributed (IID) data. This shows the general predictive limits imposed by the underlying data. In scenario (2), the samples are drawn during the optimization process, and the performance of the model is measured by calculating R-squared for

its predictions on the remaining data. To ensure a reliable performance assessment the process is repeated 25 times. This accounts for the variability of the SL sampling and the potential for overfitting, which can result from different training sample selections. The final performance of the model on each dataset is calculated as the average of the obtained R-squared values.

3.4 Description of the Data

The data sets used in this work are taken from the compilation by Xie et al. [32]. They contain formulations for alkali-activated concretes and the corresponding compressive strengths. Nine data sets of the same specimen shape, dimensions and test age were extracted. In addition, these data sets were enriched with CO₂ footprints calculated from CO₂ values of constituents obtained from the literature. Both compressive strength and CO₂ emissions are critical to selecting concrete for various applications. Table 1 gives an overview of the data sets showing the original references, the different compositions, the binder type, the number of mixes per study, the shape and dimensions of the specimens and their age at compression. Each data set contains data from an average of 10 papers and 152 formulations. This results in over 1300 materials, each described by 28 to 43 descriptive features, the corresponding compressive strength values from the laboratory, and the calculated carbon footprint. The features can be grouped into the following six categories:

- 1) The molecular composition of the binder powder is given in weight percent, which provides information on the chemical reactivity of the constituents. If only one binder is used in the concrete mix, the values are stated directly in the work. If more than one binder is used, the weighted ratio is calculated for each molecule.
- 2) The weights are given for each type of precursor, namely fly ash (FA), ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBFS), metakaolin (MK), natural pozzolan (NP), and OPC.
- 3) The weight of coarse and fine aggregates per cubic meter of concrete is given.

Table 1: Description of data sets and 95% quantile target thresholds.

Input data description							95% Target SOO		95% Target MOO	
Subset	Nr of distinct REFS	[Reference] -Materials-(Nr. of mixes)	Shape, dimensions (mm)	Testing age (days)	Nr. of formulations	Nr. of formulation parameters	Strength (MPa)	CO ₂ (kg/m ³)	Strength (MPa)	CO ₂ (kg/m ³)
1	7	[33]-FA-(8); [34]-FA-(4); [35]-FA-(17); [36]-FA-(6); [37]-FA/GGBFS-(18); [38]-FA/GGBFS-(39); [39]-FA/GGBFS-(13)	Cube, 100 ³	1	105	39	50.3	282.3	46.0	224.5
2	7	[40]-FA/OPC-(17); [41]-FA-(14); [42]-NP-(8); [43]-FA/OPC-(16); [44]-FA-(40); [45]-FA/GGBFS/OPC-(4); [46]-GGBFS-(27)	Cube, 100 ³	7	126	36	63.0	211.5	61.1	187.0
3	17	[33]-FA-(8); [47]-FA-(12); [48]-FA/GGBFS-(4); [49]-FA/GGBFS-(9); [50]-GGBFS-(12); [37]-FA-(24); [51]-GGBFS/MK-(9); [52]-FA/GGBFS-(3); [42]-NP-(17); [53]-FA-(5); [37]-PFA/GGBFS-(18); [38]-FA/GGBFS-(39); [54]-FA-(6); [39]-FA/GGBFS-(13); [45]-FA/GGBFS/OPC-(8)	Cube, 100 ³	7	188	43	56.5	137.1	54.3	137.1
4	9	[40]-FA/OPC-(17); [41]-FA-(14); [42]-NP-(8); [43]-FA/OPC-(16); [55]-FA-(9); [56]-FA-(4); [44]-FA-(40); [45]-FA/GGBFS-(4); [46]-GGBFS-(27)	Cube, 100 ³	28	139	37	68.8	198.1	64.2	187.0
5	20	[33]-FA-(8); [48]-FA/GGBFS-(7); [34]-FA-(4); [49]-FA/GGBFS-(41); [50]-GGBFS-(12); [57]-FA/GGBFS-(4); [36]-FA-(24); [51]-GGBFS/MK-(12); [52]-FA/GGBFS-(3); [42]-NP-(17); [53]-FA-(5); [58]-FA-(5); [37]-PFA/GGBFS-(17); [56]-FA-(4); [38]-FA/GGBFS-(39); [54]-FA-(6); [59]-VA/FA/RHA/GGBFS-(16); [39]-FA/GGBFS-(13); [60]-FA/GGBFS-(5); [45]-FA/GGBFS/OPC-(8)	Cube, 100 ³	28	250	43	68.0	129.4	66.9	129.4
6	4	[61]-FA-(9); [62]-FA/GGBFS-(198); [63]-FA/GGBFS-(36); [64]-FA-(31)	Cube, 150 ³	28	274	32	59.9	174.5	33.9	133.3
7	1	[65]-FA-(105)	Cylinder, 100x200	7	105	28	76.0	173.2	55.0	106.6
8	9	[66]-FA-(8); [67]-FA/GGBFS-(6); [47]-FA-(12); [68]-FA/GGBFS-(8); [69]-FA-(3); [70]-FA/OPC-(7); [71]-FA-(12); [72]-GGBFS/FA/MK/SF-(28); [73]-FA/OPC-(6)	Cylinder, 100x200	7	90	39	56.1	179.0	37.0	125.5
9	14	[66]-FA-(8); [67]-FA/GGBFS-(6); [74]-FA-(3); [75]-FA-(3); [68]-FA/GGBFS-(8); [69]-FA-(3); [70]-FA/OPC-(7); [71]-FA-(12); [76]-FA/GGBFS-(2); [77]-FA/MK/GGBFS-(13); [72]-GGBFS/FA/MK/SF-(9); [78]-FA-(5); [79]-FA/GGBFS-(5); [73]-FA/OPC-(6)	Cylinder, 100x200	28	90	38	62.3	274.7	55.8	158.2

- 4) The alkali solution is described by its chemical composition, which is characterized by a minimum of 8 and a maximum of 14 features. Specifically, two types of alkalis are described: sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and sodium silicate (Na₂SiO₃). The former is based on the dissolution of NaOH pellets in water, while the latter is commercially available and is characterized by its content of Na₂O, SiO₂ and H₂O.
- 5) The amount of additional water and/or superplasticizer is indicated. This includes the total amount of water in the concrete mix, i.e., the sum of the additional water and the water contained in the alkalis.
- 6) The curing process is described. The quantitative characteristics of the source are retained, and the non-quantitative characteristics are discarded, except for "curing at ambient temperature". In this case, 25°C is considered as the ambient temperature for curing.

The CO₂ footprint has been calculated for each mix using the approach of [80] and has been extended with a linear regression of the CO₂ footprint due to oven curing from [81]. Both factors are summarized according to the following heuristic equation:

$$CO_2 \text{ emissions } \left(\frac{t}{m^3} \right) = \sum_i w_i \cdot m_i + (0.6417 \cdot T - 16.0417) \cdot t \quad (3)$$

where:

- w_i CO₂ emissions (t) to produce 1 t of the mix component i
- m_i Mass of a mix component i in t/m³ of fresh concrete
- T Heat curing temperature if higher than 25° C; otherwise, t is set to zero
- t Curing time in days

The first part of the equation sums the carbon footprint w_i weighted with the mass of the individual precursor materials m_i . [80] provide the values shown in Table 2.

Table 2: CO₂ footprint for the precursor materials in (t CO₂)/(t precursor material).

	OPC	Fly Ash	GGBFS	Silica Fume	Metakaolin	Aggregates	Superplasticizer	NaOH Dry	Sodium silicate solution	Sodium silicate dry
w (t/t)	0.84	0.004	0.052	0.014	0.33	0.0048	1.88	1.915	0.36	1.222

The second part of equation 3 represents the cumulative emissions from heat treatment. It is modeled as a linear function that contains the curing temperature T in °C and duration t in days and is applied only to materials with the curing temperature higher than 25°C, otherwise it is set to zero (assuming that ambient curing does not contribute to carbon emissions).

4 Experimental Program

The scenarios examined are described in detail below and are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Parameters and values used in the SL material discovery approach.

	Parameter	Value
1)	Optimization target	Single objective: compressive strength f_c (max) Multi objective: compressive strength f_c (max) & CO ₂ footprint (min)
2)	Target quantile	95%
3)	Model	Gaussian Process Regression Random Forest Regression
4)	Pipeline	Vanilla Vanilla + dimensional reduction with PCA Simple grid search
5)	Strategy	Exploitation ($w_\sigma = 0$) Exploration ($w_\sigma = 2$)
6)	Initial sample size	4, 20 (batch size = 1)

First, two optimization scenarios for material design are considered. SOO is performed first, in which materials with high compressive strength are sought. This optimization represents a laboratory-driven approach, where only predicted material strength is considered for decision-making. It is the most common case in the material optimization literature.

For the second optimization target, the best compromise between CO₂ footprint and strength is sought. This optimization scenario represents a more practical-oriented approach, in which the suitability of a material for a particular application may depend on a whole range of properties that do not have to come exclusively from the laboratory.

Second, the ID method used in this study establishes a target performance threshold using a quantile measure. Specifically, a 95% target quantile is selected to represent the top 5% of material properties with the highest performance level. In other words, the optimization process is completed once a material is found that exceeds the performance level of 95% of the data set.

The material properties corresponding to this 95% performance threshold are summarized in Table 1 for each data set. To show the CO₂ savings potential, the corresponding CO₂ values have also been listed for the SOO, although they are not considered in the actual optimization. The use of the upper 95% quantile as the target criterion is motivated by the fact that the data comes from various references and may contain outliers, which could bias the estimate of the maximum strength. By using the upper 95% quantile instead of the maximum, the target criterion is based on a more robust and conservative estimate of the strength distribution, which is less susceptible to the effects of outliers.

Third, the predictive Models GPR and RF were used. Both techniques are considered non-parametric, meaning that they do not make assumptions about the functional form of the data and can flexibly adapt to complex patterns in the data [82]. One key difference between GPR and RF is the way they model uncertainty. GPR models uncertainty using a Bayesian framework, in which a probability distribution is assigned to each predicted value. This allows the model to not only make predictions, but also to provide a measure of uncertainty for each prediction. In contrast, RF does not explicitly model uncertainty and does not provide a measure of uncertainty for their predictions. However, subsampling methods such as jackknife bootstrapping enable estimating the uncertainty of a ML model's predictions [83].

In terms of performance, GPR tends to be more accurate than RF when the data is smooth and well-behaved. However, RF can be more efficient when the data is large or has complex patterns.

Overall, the choice between GPR and RF depends on the specific characteristics of the data and the goals of the prediction task. In some cases, one method may be superior to the other. However, in other cases, both methods may be suitable, and the decision will depend on the specific requirements of the application.

GPR is described in greater detail in [8] and the RF algorithm with uncertainty estimates has been introduced in [23]. For this work the scikit-learn implementation of GPR [84] and the Lolo RF [85] have been implemented.

Fourth, three different model pipelines are compared: vanilla versions of the algorithms, models evaluated after dimensional reduction using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and models tuned using a simple parameter grid and automated feature selection.

The vanilla versions of the algorithms are the simplest and most straightforward implementation of the regression models. These versions do not incorporate any additional techniques or modifications to improve the model's performance. As a result, they may not perform as well as more sophisticated approaches.

The second approach is dimensionality reduction using PCA. This technique aims to reduce the dimensionality of the data and remove redundant or irrelevant information. It is a common pre-processing technique mentioned in the literature on the implementation of ML (e.g., in [86]). In this work the dimensions were reduced such that 99% of variance of the data is kept.

The third approach involves tuning the model using a simple hyperparameters grid and automated feature selection. The hyperparameter grid contained two different kernels (isotropic and anisotropic) for GPR and two different tree depths in the case of RF. This was combined with a non-floating forward feature selector [87] that kept the eight most promising features. This selector adds features one-by-one and uses an ML model to make predictions using the given feature set at each step. The optimal configuration was chosen based on four-fold cross-validation performance. In each iteration of sequential learning, the described parameter scan was performed and the best parameters for that iteration were selected in terms of best model fit based on the R2 score metric.

Fifth, an exploiting and an exploratory strategy were investigated by setting the weight of uncertainty in the utility function (compare equation 1) to zero or two, respectively.

Six, the initial training set size has been varied between 4 and 20 samples. In each subsequent round, one sample is drawn (batch size=1) based on the utility described above. The development of completely new materials often involves working with a limited number of data points. The capacity of the laboratory can also be a limiting factor - especially if the testing task is complex and the tests are extremely expensive or lengthy. Sister samples, which are often needed for reliable analysis, can add to the expense. In such a case, the actual number of samples required for 4 test results may be much higher. On the other hand, more samples may be available if, for example,

the material is well-known and requires tweaking for a novel application such as high-performance materials or ecological re-engineering.

All calculations were conducted using the Benchmarking module of the Sequential Learning Benchmarking App [88]. The purpose of this module is to test Sequential Learning in various configurations on known datasets and compare their results to those obtained using random draws as a baseline.

Finally, the predictive power of each algorithm-pipeline combination has been assessed using the R-squared benchmark. A baseline benchmark was created using 70% randomly sampled data points as a training set and the remaining 30% as a test set. This represents a scenario where the model is trained on a large set and provides a baseline benchmarking value to compare performance to what would ideally be possible.

The benchmarks for the SL with exploit and SL with explore strategy were created using only the data sampled at the end of the material optimization to assess the prediction performance of models on materials not considered in the design process. To reduce the effect of outliers in the sampling - both during the optimization and the random sampling - the average performance is estimated over 25 repetitions for each data set. The final benchmark is the median performance over the 9 data sets.

5 Results

A total of 10,800 experiments were conducted to evaluate the performance of two prediction algorithms (RF and GPR) and three pipelines (vanilla, PCA, grid) for two different targets (SOO and MOO) using two different initial training dataset sizes (4 and 20) and an exploitative or exploratory optimization strategy. These experiments were repeated 25 times under randomized conditions on nine different datasets, resulting in 225 experiments per bar shown in the figures below for each strategy. The results are shown as the number of development cycles required to reach the target within 90% of the runs (90 % quantile of results), as an average across all data sets. A lower value indicates better performance. The results are compared against a RD as the baseline benchmark. Table 4 shows the results for all possible scenario combinations and focuses on the impact of different SL configurations on the required number of development cycles based on a single factor considered. The table shows the optimal setting in the first column and the non-optimal alternatives in the following columns. The value refers to the changes in a particular factor while keeping all other factors constant. In other words, the table shows how much the required number of

development cycles changes when only this factor is varied and all other factors remain the same.

Table 4: Best design decisions for SL configurations and potential improvement as an average of the required development cycles over nine collected data sets.

Decision	Best decision (requ. dev. cycle)	Alternative (requ. dev. cycle)	Improvement (requ. dev. cycle)
Target	MOO (13.8)	SOO (22.2)	8.4
Model	GPR (17.7)	RF (18.3)	0.6
Pipeline	Vanilla + PCA (13.7)	Vanilla (23.5) Grid Search (16.7)	9.8 3
Strategy	Exploration (15)	Exploitation (20.9)	5.9
Initial sample size	20 (13.9)	4 (22)	8.1

With an average of 18 development cycles, the use of SL methods was generally more effective than the RD, which required 44 cycles to identify the target materials in the DS, which contained an average of 152 formulations.

The size of the initial data set was found to affect the efficiency of the optimization process. Larger data sets result in faster optimization, requiring an average of 13.9 development cycles, while smaller data sets require 22 cycles. However, if only four data points are initially available, the additional acquisition of 16 data points to improve performance may not justify the savings of a mere eight experiments. Overall, the number of initial samples does not seem to affect which model-pipeline combination produces the best results, i.e., there is no approach that is particularly well suited for small initial data sets but not for larger initial data sets. Performance appears to be invariant in this regard.

Using the carbon footprint information in the MOO significantly enhanced performance by reducing the average number of development cycles to 13.8, compared to 22.2 cycles for the SOO, where only laboratory variables were used. This reduced the CO₂ footprint by more than 21% (from an average of 195 kg/m³ to 155 kg/m³), while the compressive strength decreased by only 12% from 62.3 MPa to 54.8 MPa (compare Table 1).

The optimization strategy used also impacted performance, with an exploratory approach resulting in an average of 15 development cycles compared to 20.9 cycles for the exploit strategy. This difference was more pronounced for the GPR method (8.9 cycles improvement) than for the RF method (2.9 cycles improvement).

Regarding algorithmic choice, both GPR and RF performed similarly, with a slight advantage for GPR (17.7 development cycles compared to 18.3 for RF). The choice of the pipeline configuration seems to have the strongest average impact on the SL performance.

It was found that dimensional reduction using PCA was the most effective, with an average of 13.7 development cycles compared to 23.5 cycles for the vanilla implementation and 16.7 cycles for the grid search. However, the advantage of PCA seems much more pronounced in the MOO scenario - especially for exploitative strategy. In the SOO the grid-search brings the greatest improvement for GPR. This is in line with what previous studies have reported [89]. RF benefits from the PCA pipeline in the exploit scenario and the vanilla implementation in the explore scenario. The latter is likely caused by unrealistically small uncertainties of the predictions in the dimensionally reduced space which is a disadvantage for the explorative approach.

The most challenging scenario was SOO with four initial training samples, which required an average of 18.5 development cycles even with the best available algorithms. In contrast, the ecologically informed MOO scenario with 4 initial samples was much more feasible, requiring an average of only four development cycles. The best configurations for the SOO and MOO scenarios with either four or twenty initial training samples are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5: Ideal SL configuration results for different scenarios in terms of algorithm, pipeline and strategy.

Scenario	4 init. sample (requ. dev. cycle.)	20 init. Sample (requ. dev. cycle.)
SOO	Explore GPR grid search (18.5)	Explore GPR grid search (10.7)
MOO	Explore GPR+PCA (4.4)	Explore GPR + PCA or Exploit RF + PCA (4.7)

Finally, the model performance has been assessed (see Table 6). The best baseline result in terms of sheer predictive performance was achieved with the vanilla RF base model, closely followed by the RF + grid search model. While an R-squared of less

than 0.8 is not an outstanding performance, it can be explained by the inconsistent data from globally distributed laboratories and by the relatively small average data set size. Outliers are to be expected due to the inconsistency of the data, and the sampling distribution is also likely to be sparse in some areas. These have a large negative effect on R². Overall, the GPR models perform worse than the RF models in terms of pure predictive performance. This could be due to the actual inferiority of the GPR algorithm or the nature of the data, which are largely discontinuous as they come from different references. The latter presents a greater obstacle for the GPR models, which model with continuous distribution functions. The PCA pipeline improves the performance of the Gaussian process models but has mixed results for the random forest models, and the grid search pipeline generally performs well for both models.

Table 6: Benchmarking model performance for different algorithm pipeline combinations as the median R-squared over the mean performance from 25 randomized runs on 9 datasets.

Algorithm	Baseline performance	SL with exploit strategy	SL with explore strategy
GPR vanilla	0.05	0.12	0.27
GPR vanilla + PCA	0.35	-0.02	0.05
GPR grid search	0.08	-0.17	0.08
RF vanilla	0.79	0.36	0.42
RF vanilla + PCA	0.70	0.01	0.06
RF grid search	0.69	0.15	0.22

Exploration leads to more broadly distributed training data and thus more representative samples. Therefore, it was also expected that this would lead to a better training base, which in turn would contribute to better generalization of the models.

The most accurate predictions at the end of SL can be achieved with the RF model. However, an R-square of 0.42 corresponds only to a rough estimate of the general trend in the formulations. While the grid search pipeline created solid baseline results for both models it could not deliver the same performance for the smaller training samples at the end of SL, which suggests overfitting. Vanilla models always perform best. Overall, the benchmarking of model performance does not provide any indication of the models' suitability for SL.

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Figure 2: Benchmarking SL in terms of mean required development cycles in 25 randomized runs on 9 different data sets for different algorithm-pipeline combinations with different initial sample size to achieve target with exploit strategy (weight of uncertainty=0) in single objective optimization (left) and multi objective optimization (right) with 90% success probability.

Figure 3: Benchmarking SL in terms of mean required development cycles in 25 randomized runs on 9 different data sets for different algorithm-pipeline combinations with different initial sample size to achieve target with explore strategy (weight of uncertainty=2) in single objective optimization (left) and multi objective optimization (right) with 90% success probability.

6 Discussion and Conclusions

Compliance with the Paris climate agreement will not be possible without reducing emissions from cement production. The complex chemical reactions of their many components make it difficult to find usable alternatives. A classical experimental design approach reaches its limits, as thousands of experiments would be required to cover all possible combinations of starting materials. This is where SL comes into play: It shifts a large part of the task to ML predictions. Its acceleration potential lies in omitting unimportant experiments and finding materials with desired properties quicker through a targeted series of experiments. Compared to conventional data-based predictions, the emphasis is on data collection in the laboratory that is as parsimonious as it is effective.

The central hypothesis of this study was confirmed: The configuration of the AI-driven materials design, including the model selection, hyperparameter settings, and optimization strategy (as shown in Table 3), was found to have a significant impact on the expected performance. The best configuration resulted in a tenfold increase in performance compared to the least effective configuration (see Figure 2 and 3).

The first research question was addressed by conducting an in-depth analysis of each parameter's influence, with the results summarized in Table 4. Based on these findings, an ideal strategy could be derived that aligns well with empirical results from SL benchmarking, as indicated in Table 5. Specifically, dimensionality reduction using PCA led to the highest algorithmic improvement overall, while for SOO, GPR with grid search produced the best performance. The most feasible scenario was found to be MOO between a prediction and an a-priori available information. Notably, incorporating a-priori information into the design is seldom mentioned in the literature, but it can significantly improve SL-optimization performance (see Figure 2 and 3, right).

Regarding the second research question, the analysis showed that SL demonstrated significant acceleration compared to complete screening and the statistical RD baseline, as demonstrated by Figure 2 and 3. In the optimal scenario, less than 5% of the formulations were sampled with SL to reach the target with high certainty, compared to 100% for complete screening and 25% for RD.

Finally, the analysis of the third research question showed that accurate predictions of material properties can be made in principle using the Random Forest (RF) algorithm, but only if a representative data sample is available (as shown in Table 6). Surprisingly, the model prediction performance and SL optimization performance were not

correlated, meaning that the best model performance did not necessarily lead to the best SL performance. While more advanced pipelines, which are aimed at improving model accuracy, can improve optimization performance in some scenarios, the pure predictive accuracy of the model does not seem to be a suitable indicator of overall usefulness. Here, simulated experiments are more appropriate because they directly measure the optimization performance regarding required development cycles.

These results challenge the usual emphasis on model accuracy in data-driven material development in civil engineering and show that valuable insights can be gained even with limited data sets and high input complexity. The exploration of different optimization scenarios and predictive accuracy led to relevant solutions, although AI currently cannot fully replace laboratory work. This promises immediate effectiveness in complex material development challenges.

The data collected also show that there does not appear to be a serious trade-off between environmental sustainability and the mechanical performance of materials. This suggests that designs can achieve high material quality while being environmentally sound. By incorporating a broader range of factors such as cost, resource availability, and other properties into materials development, this approach can revolutionize how complex building materials are researched and designed.

7 Limitations and future research potential

The key limitation of using ML in material science is its black-box nature. Despite the high confidence in the results produced by ML algorithms, researchers may need a deeper understanding of the relationships between the properties of a material and its performance. This requires careful configuration of the ML models. The success may be highly dependent on the quality and size of the training data. It is challenging to ensure that it is successful for the desired materials and applications. Nevertheless, this work has demonstrated that only a few iterations are necessary to achieve excellent optimization performance.

The data on which this study is based comes from numerous publications conducted in laboratories around the globe. This means that this data is likely to be more inconsistent than data from one lab. With more consistent data coming from one source, SL performance is expected to increase even further.

Furthermore, each reference contains a small number of samples on average leading to a fractured locally populated and sparse search space. In a real laboratory application, the search space would be populated more globally. This not only leads to

a completely new set of research questions which cannot be addressed with the presented approach (such as the construction of the search space [90] or multi-fidelity optimization [91]), but it may also put the conclusions that were drawn here into a novel perspective.

Future research should focus on developing data-driven approaches to building materials optimization, with the aim of automating the process and implementing the approach at larger scales. Although other materials science domains have seen success with automated platforms, there has been limited automation of experiments in the building materials sector. Consequently, research should focus on more high-throughput and/or automated experiments to optimize or discover new materials.

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Declaration of interests and data availability

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. The data and source code necessary to reproduce the results will be made available according to F.A.I.R. standards upon the acceptance of this contribution.

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